

Publication Guideline

January 2024

This document is provided by: Euroseeds and Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI)

PRO CONSULTING

UNIVERSITY OF LATVIA

INRAE

DANISH TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE

ILVO

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety

UNIVERSITÄT BAYREUTH

Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação

HZPC

INVE

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Funded by the European Union

1. Introduction

What is Open Science? It is an approach to research based on open cooperative work that emphasizes the sharing of knowledge, results and tools as early and widely as possible. It operates on the principle of being '**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**'.

Open Science practices need to be assured by Horizon Europe beneficiaries

(see chapter 16 Open Science of the [HE Programme Guide](#))!

This includes **ensuring open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications**.

GeneBEcon beneficiaries shall comply to following publishing rules for scientific publications:

- 1) As soon as the publication is accessible, **a machine-readable electronic copy** of the publication needs to be **deposited in a trusted repository** (e.g., [Zenodo](#) or [bioRxiv](#)).
- 2) **Open access is immediately** provided to the deposited publication.
- 3) Provide information about any research output or any other tools needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.
- 4) **Sufficient intellectual property rights must be retained** to comply with the open access requirements.
- 5) **Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications** are eligible for reimbursement.

General rules for open science and access in Horizon Europe can be found here:

<https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-publications>

<https://zenodo.org/records/7738501#.ZBfwoC9XZQY>

2. What do you need to do before starting to write a publication?

- 1) **Did you clarify the authors?** Clarify authors involved before drafting your publication. Did you use any other partners' background or results? Did you collaborate with other beneficiaries in your research? If yes, get in contact with them. Write down the shares of author contributions.

General rules for authorship declarations in scientific publications can be found here:

<https://credit.niso.org/>

<https://publicationethics.org/guidance/Guidelines>

- 2) **Did you clarify publishing costs?** Who will pay for the open access publication fee? The main author or will the costs be divided? Are there any contractual agreements between your institution and the publisher? What are the conditions?

3. What do you need to do when you have the publication draft?

- 1) **Did you inform the consortium about the dissemination of results well in time?** As defined in the CA, when intending to disseminate its results, **a partner must give at least 30 days advance of the submission of the manuscript notice to the consortium**, providing sufficient information on the results it will disseminate (Section 8.4). Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement **by written notice (by email) to the coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice**. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.
- 2) Did you acknowledge the HEU funding of your project in the manuscript?
- 3) Did you inform the WP on communication, dissemination and exploitation before the publication is published so that they can prepare communication material about your work?